

Kinetics of Ruthenium(III)-catalysed Oxidation of Aromatic Azo Compounds by Sodium Metaperiodate—Kinetic Method of Determination of Ruthenium(III)

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The kinetics of oxidation of aromatic azo compounds of the general structure $R-C_6H_4-N=N-C_6H_4N(CH_3)_2$, where $R=H, Cl, COOH, NO_2$, by sodium metaperiodate, catalysed by Ru^{III} was investigated. The reaction is first order with respect to the substrate and Ru^{III} . The observation of Michaelis type of kinetics with periodate ion, under the conditions $[periodate] \gg [Ru^{III}]$, suggests the formation of 1 : 1 complex between the catalyst and periodate, which is the reactive species. The catalysed reaction was utilised for developing a kinetic method for the determination of Ru^{III} in nanogram amounts with an average error of 1%.

MANY periodate oxidations are catalysed by Ru^{III} . The Ru^{III} -catalysed oxidations of nitrophenols¹, benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehydes², arene³, dimethyl sulphoxide⁴, maleic, fumaric and acrylic acids, styrene⁵ and stilbene were reported. Similar type of kinetic behaviour in the case of Ru^{III} -catalysed oxidations of cycloalkanols has also been reported⁶. The present authors have found that periodate is unreactive towards the aromatic azo compounds in $0.1-0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} HClO_4$, whereas traces of Ru^{III} catalyses the reaction. The authors found that the kinetic behaviour of this reaction is different from the one reported by Murthy *et al.* for the other Ru^{III} -catalysed oxidations of organic compounds. The present reaction was found to obey first order kinetics with respect to substrate and Ru^{III} . The reaction is inhibited by H^+ ion. On the other hand, the other Ru^{III} -catalysed oxidations of organic compounds reported earlier obey first order kinetics with respect to substrate and Ru^{III} but zero order kinetics with respect to periodate. The authors have also calculated the ionisation constant of periodic acid from the analysis of the rate data and the value thus obtained is in reasonable agreement with the reported value. They have further developed a catalytic method for the estimation of Ru^{III} in nanogram amounts based on this catalysed reaction. The method has the advantage that Ru can be determined in nanogram amounts and Os, Fe *etc.* do not interfere.

Experimental

All the materials employed were of analytical reagent grade. All solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The course of the reaction was followed by measuring the optical density of the unreacted azo compound at 510 nm where each of the azo compounds has been found to have maximum absorption and obeys Beer's law and all

other materials concerned have negligible absorption under these conditions. The kinetic runs were carried out maintaining the ionic strength constant with sodium perchlorate. Under the experimental conditions employed for the investigation of the catalysed reaction, the rate of the uncatalysed reaction was found to be negligibly small and hence no correction was made while analysing the rate data.

Stoichiometry: To investigate the stoichiometry of the reaction, a known excess of each of the azo compounds was mixed with a known concentration of sodium metaperiodate in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} perchloric acid in presence of 10% (v/v) acetic acid and $2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} Ru^{III}$ and kept for 24 h at 30° . The optical density of the unreacted azo compound was determined at 510 nm from which its concentration was calculated using the value of its molar extinction coefficient. The results show that for all the azo compounds employed as substrates, one mole of sodium meta periodate reacts with one mole of the azo compound. The uv spectral study and the spot-test⁷ have shown that the product of oxidation is the corresponding azoxy compound.

Results and Discussion

The reaction was found to be first order in the substrate as shown by the linearity of \log (optical density) vs time plots, under the pseudo-first order condition, $[Periodate] \gg [Substrate]$. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_1) were calculated from the slopes of the plots.

Effect of Ru^{III} and sodium metaperiodate: The values of k_1 were also determined at different sodium metaperiodate and Ru^{III} concentrations. Plot of k_1 vs $[Ru^{III}]$ was found to be a straight line passing through origin showing that the reaction

Fig. 1. Effect of [Periodate] on the oxidation of *p*-NO₂ BADMA : [p-NO₂ BADMA]=1.724 × 10⁻², [Ru^{III}]=2 × 10⁻², and [H⁺]=1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³; μ=3.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻²; HOAc=10% (v/v).

is first order with respect to Ru^{III}. The dependence of the rate on [periodate] was shown by the plot 1/k₁ vs 1/[periodate] which is a straight line with a positive intercept and slope (Fig. 1).

Effect of [H⁺] ion on the rate : The pseudo-first order rate constants (k₁) were also determined at different concentrations of perchloric acid by keeping the ionic strength constant with sodium perchlorate. The results show that the reaction is retarded by H⁺ ion. The plot of 1/k₁ vs [H⁺] was found to be a straight line with a positive intercept on the 1/k₁ axis.

Mechanism : The dependence of rate on the concentration of periodate, Ru^{III} and the substrate indicate that all these species participate in the rate-limiting step. The observance of Michaelis type of kinetics with respect to periodate ion, under the conditions [periodate] ≫ [Ru^{III}], suggests the formation of a 1 : 1 complex between catalyst and periodate ion, the complex being the reactive oxidising species. The uv and Raman spectral studies⁸⁻¹¹ indicate that in aqueous acid media (<5 M), perio-

date mainly exists in the form of tetrahedral IO₄⁻ and the octahedral H₄IO₆⁻, and H₆IO₆ and at higher acidities it is further protonated giving H₆IO₆⁺ or I(OH)₆⁺. Crouthamel *et al.*¹² have reported the apparent ionisation constant (K'₁) is related as

$$K'_1 = \frac{a_{H^+}(a_{IO_4^-} + a_{H_4IO_6^-})}{a_{H_6IO_6}} = 2.3 \times 10^{-2} \quad (1)$$

Galliford *et al.*¹⁰ reported that at pH < 2, the dilute periodate solutions are mainly in the form of H₆IO₆ and IO₄⁻. Hence under these conditions which also pertain to the experimental conditions employed by the authors, H₄IO₆⁻ activity is believed to be negligibly small.

The oxidation of Ru^{III} by periodate is known to be very fast¹³. Thus it appears that the conversion of Ru^{III} to Ru^{VIII} takes place much more rapidly than the oxidation of the azo compound. Hence, it is reasonable to postulate that Ru^{VIII} is the species responsible for the catalysis. Reports¹⁴ are available in the literature that in the acid medium, Ru^{VIII} is present in the form of H₂RuO₄.

or $\text{RuO}_3(\text{OH})_2$ with the first acid dissociation constant of $(6.8 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-12}$. To explain the kinetic results, it is proposed that a complex between H_2RuO_4 and H_2IO_6 is formed which acts as the active oxidising species. The electron transfer probably takes place via Ru^{VIII} centre which abstracts electrons from the azo compound in the rate-determining stage forming Ru^{VI} which is rapidly oxidised by periodate to Ru^{VIII} . This can be represented by the following scheme,

It is interesting to note that a similar mechanism of electron transfer was proposed by Rozovskii¹⁰ for the ruthenium-catalysed oxidation of Cu^{II} by periodate.

The mechanism leads to the rate law,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{Azo compound}]}{dt}$$

$$= k[\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}} - \text{Periodate complex}][\text{Azo compound}]$$

$$= \frac{k K_1 K_2 [\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}}]_t [\text{Periodate}]_t [\text{Substrate}]_t}{[\text{H}^+] + K_1 + K_1 K_2 [\text{Periodate}]_t}$$

$[\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}}]_t$, being equal to $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_t$, the total concentration of Ru^{III} and the pseudo-first order rate constant

(k_1) under the conditions, $[\text{periodate}]_t \gg [\text{substrate}]_t$ is given by

$$k_1 = \frac{k K_1 K_2 [\text{Periodate}]_t [\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}}]_t}{[\text{H}^+] + K_1 + K_1 K_2 [\text{Periodate}]_t} \quad (3)$$

According to equation (3), plots of $1/k_1$ vs $[\text{H}^+]$ and $1/k_1$ vs $1/[\text{Periodate}]_t$ must be straight lines with positive slopes and positive intercepts. Such plots were obtained showing the validity of

TABLE 1—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANT (k) AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

Substrate*	$\times 10^4 k, \text{s}^{-1} \text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$			$E_a \pm 1$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger \pm 3$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	30°	35°	40°		
Methyl orange	20.08	22.22	24.65	17	96
p-Cl BADMA	13.55	15.97	17.45	23	90
p-COOH BADMA	7.80	9.81	12.95	24	88
p-NO ₂ BADMA	2.86	3.51	4.32	32	85

* BADMA = Benzene azo dimethyl aniline.

TABLE 2—FIRST APPARENT IONISATION CONSTANT OF PERIODIC ACID (K_1') EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT OF THE COMPLEX (K_2)

$[\text{H}^+] = 3.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 30 ± 0.1

Substrate	$\times 10^3 K_1'$ mol dm ⁻³	K_2 mol dm ⁻³
Methyl orange	2.31	1.844
p-Cl BADMA	2.52	1.860
p-COOH BADMA	2.44	1.832
p-NO ₂ BADMA	2.63	1.870

Fig. 2. Calibration curve for estimation of Ru^{III} .

the rate law and hence the mechanism. From the slopes of these plots, the rate constant of the rate-limiting step and K_1' , the apparent ionisation constant of periodate and K_2 , the stability constant of the intermediate complex, were calculated and this investigation was repeated at different temperatures. The activation energy of the rate-determining step was determined (Tables 1 and 2).

Catalytic kinetic determination of Ru^{III} in nanogram amounts: The authors have employed the Ru^{III}-catalysed oxidation of methyl orange by periodate as the basis reaction for the development of a kinetic method for the determination of Ru^{III} in nanograms (1–9 ng ml⁻¹). It has been found that the decrease in the optical density, Δx exactly after 10 min is directly proportional to Ru^{III} concentration in nanogram range at an acid concentration of 0.1 mol dm⁻³ at 30°. Hence, the authors recommend the following procedure for the kinetic determination of Ru^{III}. Calculated amounts of methyl orange and perchloric acid to give an overall concentration of 1.77×10^{-3} and 0.1 mol dm⁻³, respectively, are mixed with a known fixed volume of Ru^{III} solution and water and thermostated. Periodate solution is also kept in the same thermostat. After temperature equilibrium is attained, calculated volume of periodate, to give an overall concentration of 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ (overall volume 25 ml), is added simultaneously. The optical density at zero time is measured for the same solution without Ru^{III}. The decrease in optical density after 10 min gives Δx . The Δx value was determined at different Ru^{III} concentrations and Δx is plotted against [Ru^{III}] (which serves as a calibration curve), which has been found to be a straight line passing through origin (Fig. 2). The Δx value is determined for a known volume

of the unknown concentration of Ru^{III} and its concentration obtained from the calibration curve.

In the estimation of Ru^{III}, the interference of various ions were studied. Cu^{II}, Ag^I, V^V, V^{IV}, Cr^{VI}, Mo^{VI}, As^{III}, Mn^{II}, Na^I, K^I, Mg^{II} and Ni^{II} ions did not have any effect on the accuracy of the estimation even when their concentrations are 400 times to that of Ru^{III}. The ions Fe^{III}, Os^{VIII} and W^{VI} did not interfere with the estimation even when they are present in amounts 100 times greater than the amount of Ru^{III}.

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